

Misconceptions and Associated Errors Made by Basic 7 Learners in Fractions

Nero Kukulaje ✉

Department of Mathematics, Navrongo Senior High School, Ghana

Bright Awelana Bakiweyem

School of Teacher Education, Florida State University, USA

Ambrose Kombat

Department of Mathematics, St. Bernadette's Technical Institute, Ghana

Abstract

The study's aim was to determine misconception and errors made by basic 7 learners in fractions in the Kasena-Nankana Municipal in the Upper East Region of Ghana. The study also assessed the possible causes of the misconceptions and errors made by the learners. The research approach used was mixed methods and the design was convergent parallel. The sample size was sixty-three (63) learners selected from two intact Basic 7 classes using purposive sampling. Data was gathered using test and interviews. Errors were analysis using content analysis and interview was analysis thematically. The results indicated that learners made conceptual and procedural errors and the major misconception was learners overgeneralizing the idea of dealing with numerators separately from denominators as it is done in multiplication of fractions and addition/subtraction of whole numbers into addition and subtraction of fractions, and also assuming that fractions with largest denominators are always the lesser fractions. The interview finding also reveal that learners' misconceptions and errors were due to (1) learners perceived ideas (perception) about mathematics and (2) Methods of instruction by teachers.

Keywords: *misconceptions, Errors, fractions.*

Suggested citation: Kukulaje, N., Bakiweyem, B.A., & Kombat, A. (2024). Misconceptions and Associated Errors Made by Basic 7 Learners in Fractions. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(6), 275-286. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(6).18

Introduction

One of the basic and most challenging topics in mathematics is fractions. The acquisition of such a topic is so important that learners must achieve mastery of it starting with the first year of elementary school through secondary education (Alacaci, 2010). Additionally, it is well recognized that fractions are crucial in teaching complex mathematical concepts like algebra (Redmond, 2009). It is crucial for learners to

understand fractions because they are essential for understanding algebra and many other complex mathematical ideas. (Siegler, Fazio, Bailey, & Zhou, 2013).

A broad and increasing consensus exist among mathematic educators that the fraction concept is one of the most universal, diverse, and important mathematical concepts that learners come into contact with before they reach high school (Siemon et al., 2015). Smith (2002) asserts that learners are exposed to fraction concepts even before they begin formal education and continue through high school. However, Student difficulty persists despite this early exposure.

Understanding fractions is likely the biggest obstacles to children's mathematical development (Fairchild, 2013). Therefore, it is important that educators stress the value of core mathematical concepts in the early learning phases rather than placing a heavy emphasis on memorizing procedures and rules through drill and practice techniques. According to Vamvakoussy and Vosniadou, (2010), Students grow their understanding of mathematics by building on what they have already learned. Because of this, any misconceptions they may have when they learn the subject could impair how they learn related mathematical topics in the future. It is therefore crucial that these misunderstandings are recognized as quickly as feasible in order to assist students in correcting them and thereby enabling future comprehension of more complex and connected topics. A person's incorrect beliefs and guiding principles are known as misconceptions, and they can lead to learners making a string of mistakes, Fakude and Makonye (2016). Also, Ojose (2015) argues that a misconception is a concept that has been misunderstood and misinterpreted.

Extant literature has shown that misconception is a phenomenon that exists across the globe. For example, in Turkey, Aksoy and Yazlik (2017) investigated students' mistakes and misconceptions of 5th and 6th grades in fractions and operations with fractions using a qualitative research design and purposive sampling technique. The finding showed that learners have misconceptions and mistakes about fractions.

In another study, Erohlu (2012) studied potential teachers' (teacher trainees) knowledge and mistakes held by elementary students in fractions. It was discovered that potential elementary school instructors could identify the learners' fractional errors. The results further revealed that students' 'misconceptions of fractions' could be overcome by using real-life models, drills and practices, simple and counter-examples, reviewing prior knowledge, teaching standard algorithms, enhancing motivation, and bringing students' attention to their errors.

In addition, an investigation of the existence of errors and misconceptions in Saudi Arabia among college students revealed that college students have false beliefs regarding fractions and mathematic computations containing fractions like; believing that all fractions are always part of one and never more than one (Algahzo & Algahzo, 2016).

Again, Lee and Boyadzhiev, (2020) also investigated the understanding of and misconceptions regarding fractions among students in the college and found that a lack of knowledge of the fundamental definitions of the concept of fraction, least common denominators/least common multiples, and order of operations among learners was linked to their misconceptions.

In South Africa in the province of Limpopo, Makonye (2010) investigated the mathematical mistakes and misunderstandings of students in grade 12. According to the author, learners' misconceptions of mathematics were a result of the knowledge gap in algebra and excessive reliance on procedural knowledge without conceptual

support. Makhubele (2021) also noted in his research on fractions that the main source of misconceptions and errors in fractions was due to the learners' past knowledge, their inability to grasp the fundamental ideas, and their improper application of the rules.

Deringol's (2019) research revealed that mathematics teachers and prospective teachers came to the conclusion that when it came to reading and writing fractions, distinguishing between different types of fractions, representing fraction on a number line, ordering of fractions and performing operation on fraction, learners at the primary school had problems. They also had problems understanding the denominator and numerator concepts.

Alkhateeb (2019) study revealed the following misconceptions; one of the misconceptions was that learners believe that the figure x/y is always less than one and that a fractional number is always greater than that figure. Also learners treating the fractions as an integer, misinterpreting fractions, and ignoring the integer in the fractional numbers. Aksoy and Yazlik (2017), noted that students' misunderstanding and mistakes about fractions most especially with operations with fractions are a course of concern.

Ramadianti, Priatna, and Kusnandi (2019) identify the following as some misconceptions students experienced:

- 1) interpreting fraction as part of a whole,
- 2) as quotient,
- 3) as a ratio,
- 4) as a measure.

These misunderstandings occurred because learners experienced limited context to work with fractions, Ramadianti et.al (2019). According to Ghani and Maat (2017), mistakes and misconceptions were made by students when they added two fractions with distinct denominators. In Ghana, Amuah, Davis, and Fletche (2019) studied students' misconceptions of fractions and note that students have least understanding of the equivalence concept in fractions, though they showed good understanding of the part-whole concept in fractions. Also, research by Agbozoo and Fletcher (2020), on prospective teachers' understanding of fractions revealed that prospective teachers are unable to explain the logic behind how the procedure for dividing a fraction by a fraction operates. Additionally, the participants were unable to come up with a method for teaching fraction division based on their pedagogical subject knowledge of fractions.

Iddrisu and Alhassan (2017) found that the common misconceptions and errors in elementary arithmetic among students at the University for Development Studies (UDS) and Navrongo Senior High School (Navasco) in Ghana were mostly caused by a lack of conceptual understanding and algebraic competence or abilities.

Per the above literature, it can be observed that misconceptions and errors in fractions have been a major challenge at the school level and in higher institutions and many studies have been conducted in that regard. However much has not been done in terms of research on this topic in the context of this study hence the need for this piece.

Materials and Methods

The research methodology employed is a mixed-method approach. In order to present a fuller and more comprehensive picture of a topic, mixed-method research is a strategy that incorporates quantitative and qualitative methodologies into a single study (Creswell, 2014). According to Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009), the current study can be classified as QUAN+QUAL, which denotes a predominance of quantitative methods and subsequent use of qualitative methods (student interviews), which provide additional information and support the quantitative findings. The research strategy that is employed is a convergent mixed-method design. In this design, contradictions or inconsistent results are explained or further explored (Creswell, 2018). In a convergent parallel design, the researcher simultaneously conducts the quantitative and qualitative components while giving each method equal weight, analyzing the two elements separately, and interpreting the results together (Creswell & Pablo-Clark, 2011). With the purpose of corroboration and validation, the researcher aims to throw more light on discovered problems identified in the quantitative phase and then use the qualitative findings to determine the cause of the problems. The study's research methodology uses a convergent mixed-parallel design. The mixed method was used by administering an achievement test (pretest and post-test) and semi-structured interviews as research tools in order to gather quantitative and qualitative data respectively. The data from the pretest, and post-test were analyzed using content analysis, and descriptive statistics, as well as recordings of the interview, were transcribed and analyzed to back the results of the pretest and post-test.

Results and Discussions

This section discusses analysis of the information which was generated based on the research questions.

Research question one: What types of misconceptions and associated errors do Basic seven learners have on fractions?

In order to respond to research question 1; types of misconceptions and associated errors basic seven learners make, the researcher analyzed learners' pre-test marked scripts. The analysis was first done by way of calculating percentages for (1) learners who answered the questions correctly, (2) those who had incorrect responses, and (3) learners who did not attempt the questions at all. After that, content analysis was performed on the marked scripts. Examining the answers of students from the pre-test questions in addition and subtracting fractions with similar and different denominators is shown in table 1 below.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Values of Learners' Responses to Questions on Addition and Subtraction of Fraction

Question	Correct		Incorrect		Unanswered	
	f	%	F	%	F	%
Q1,2	7	22.6	23	74.2	1	3.2
Q3	10	32.3	21	67.7	0	0
Q4,6	11	35.5	18	58.0	2	6.5
Q5	4	12.9	26	83.9	1	3.2

Source: Field data, 2024

Item 1 and 2 (Addition of fractions with different denominators)

Questions 1 and 2 of the pre-tests (see appendix A) were on addition of fractions with different denominators. While 7(22.6%) provided correct responses, there were common mistakes noticeably in those learners (f=23, 74.2%) who failed to provide correct responses with one (3.2%) learner not answering the question at all. A content analysis of learners' marked script demonstrated that most of the students answered question 1 and 2 by adding the numerators of the given fractions together and the denominators together to obtain the answer $\frac{5}{7}$ for question 1 and $\frac{7}{13}$ for question 2 thereby committing two forms of errors (conceptual and procedural errors). This is exemplified by learners marked script below:

1. Solve $\frac{3}{2} + \frac{2}{5}$

Answer:

$3 + 2 = 5$

$2 + 5 = 7$

Explain:

I answer it like this because the 3 and the 2 are all in one line side that is why. and i answer all of the like that

2. Solve $\frac{5}{6} + \frac{2}{7}$

Answer:

$5 + 2 = 7$

$6 + 7 = 13$

$= 20$

Figure 1. Sample of Learners Work on Addition of Fraction

It is evident that the learners misapplied the rule of multiplication of fractions for addition of fractions. This is because when multiplying fractions, the numerators are multiplied as are the denominators. The researcher, therefore, concludes that grade 7 learners lack a basic comprehension of addition in fractions because of the misapplication of the rule for multiplying fractions to the addition of fractions. This finding is in agreement with what Makhubele (2021) stated – learners commit errors when adding fractions because of comprehension gap of the basic concept, misconceptions, and misapplication of rules as well as learners' prior knowledge.

Item 3 (Addition of fractions with the same denominator)

Question 3 was on the addition of fractions with the same denominators. With this question, 10(32.3%) of learners provided correct responses, with (f=21, 67.7%) providing incorrect responses to the question. These learners who failed to provide correct responses exhibited the same mistakes in their work. They solved the question in the same way it was done for questions 1 and 2. Learners added the numerators of the fractions separately and the denominators separately to show their responses. A sample of learners' work is shown in the figure 2 below:

3. Simplify $\frac{4}{3} + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{3}$

Answer:

$$\frac{4}{3} + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{3} = \frac{7}{3}$$

Explain:

Add the numerators

Figure 2: Sample of Learners Work on Addition of Fraction

Item 4 and 6 (Subtraction of fractions)

Questions 4 and 6 were centered on the subtraction of fractions with different denominators. While 11 (35.5%) learners were able to provide correct responses, more than half 18 (58.1%) of the learners got the questions wrong with similar mistakes in their responses. In addition, 2 (6.5%) of learners did not attempt the questions at all. Learners' approaches, to solving these questions were not different from the way they answered the additional questions. They subtracted the numerators and the denominators separately to arrive at their answers. In some cases, some of the learners knew they required least common multiple (LCM) to be able to solve the question. LCM was correctly obtained but ended up getting the result wrong (see figure 3). This result was confirmed by Almeda et al. (2013), who demonstrated that lower-grade students still find it difficult to simplify fractions, many of them employing the wrong rule to answer fractional problems.

Solve the following

4. $\frac{3}{4} - \frac{1}{4}$

Answer:

$$\frac{3}{4} - \frac{1}{4} = \frac{2}{4} = 2$$

Explain:

you will have to do $3 - 1 = 2$ it means
so your answer is 2

6. $\frac{7}{13} - \frac{5}{13}$

Answer:

$$\frac{7}{13} - \frac{5}{13} = \frac{70-62}{13} = \frac{12}{13}$$

Explain:

first find the common multiple of the denominators and use 13 to multiply the numerators.

Solve the questions below

Figure 3. Sample of Learners Work on the Addition of Fraction

Items 7 and 9 (multiplication of proper fractions)

In questions 7 and 9, learners were asked to multiply two proper fractions. While 9 (29%) provided correct responses, there were mistakes made by 18 learners representing 58.1% who failed to provide correct responses. Also, 4 (12.9%) of learners did not attempt the question at all.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Values of Learners' Responses to Questions on Multiplication of Proper Fractions

Questions	Correct		Incorrect		Unanswered	
	f	%	f	%	F	%
Q7, Q9	9	29.0	18	58.1	4	12.9

Source: field data, 2024.

A review of the scripts of the learners who couldn't answer the questions revealed that some errors were made by the learners. It was observed that these learners answered the question by cross-multiplying the numerator of the first fraction with the denominator of the second fraction (see figure 4). This finding confirms the position of Wong and Evans (2011). The authors observed that multiplication of numerators and denominators is a fundamental mistake made by primary school children. It was also noticed that learners only multiply the numerators and maintain one denominator. This misconception is an overgeneralization of the algorithm for adding like fractions. This finding was also supported by the finding of Alghazo and Alghazo, (2017).

Figure 4. Sample of Learners Work on Multiplication of Fractions

Item 8

Again, to establish learners' understanding of the multiplication of fractions, participants were given a whole number and proper fraction to multiply. Table 3 presents descriptive statistics on the number of learners who responded correctly to the question, those who had them wrong, and learners who did not attempt the question.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Values of Learners' Responses to Questions on Multiplication of Whole Numbers and a Proper Fraction

Question	Correct		Incorrect		Unanswered	
	F	%	f	%	F	%
Q8	5	16.1%	19	61.3	7	22.6

Source: Field data, 2024

In question 8 which was on multiplying a whole number and a proper fraction. 5 (16.1%) learners provided correct responses, 19 (61.3%) of learners failed to provide correct answers to the question, 7 (22.6%) of learners left the question blank, majority of learners multiply the whole number with both numerator and denominator which shows that learners do not understand the concept well. Again, learners also added the whole number with the numerator and denominator of the fractions which was a demonstration of a lack of information about what to do and others actually knew what to do but got the procedure wrong. The misconception that led to most of the errors was the overgeneralization of the whole number multiplication rule. This finding was supported by the findings of Azurah, Mohd, Johar, et al. (2014) who came to the conclusion that students frequently apply the addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division rules incorrectly using the same techniques without taking the association idea into account. Below is a sample response.

Figure 5. Sample of Learners Work on Multiplication of Whole Numbers and a Proper Fraction

Item 10a and 10b (ordering of fractions with the same and different denominators)

The analysis of students' responses regarding the ordering of fractions with the same denominators (Q10a) and those with different denominators(Q10b) is shown in table 4.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Values of Learners' Responses to the Ordering of Fractions with the Same and Different Denominators

Question	Correct		Incorrect		Unanswered	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
Q(10a)	11	35.4	10	32.3	10	32.3
Q(10b)	8	25.8	10	32.3	13	41.9

Source: Field data, 2024

Questions 10a and 10b were focused on the ordering of fractions with similar and different denominators in ascending order. While 11(35.4%) and 8 (25.8%) provided

correct responses respectively to questions 10a and 10b, (f=10, 32.3%) failed to provide the correct response to each of the questions respectively with 10(32.3%) and 13(41.9%) of learners not attempting questions 10a and 10b respectively at all. It was observed that learners think that fractions with larger denominators are the lesser fractions when ordering. It was again observed that learners were adding and subtraction the numerators and the denominators of fractions they were supposed to order which was an indication that they lack conceptual understanding of ordering fractions (see figure 6). This finding confirms the findings by Johar and Zakaria, (2015), who stated that pupils choose fractions with a larger denominator $\frac{2}{5}$ as smaller than $\frac{1}{3}$ in ordering as their answer because they thought that a bigger denominator means a lesser fraction, and also (Hamdan & Gunderson, 2017) discovered that students erroneously think that $\frac{1}{8}$ is large and $\frac{1}{2}$ is small.

(b). $\frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{6}$

Answer:

$\frac{5}{6}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{1}{2}$ (circled)

Explain:

the fraction that have the bigger down number is small one

Arrange these fractions in order from the smallest to the largest (ascending order)

10 (a). $\frac{1}{2}, \frac{4}{5}, \frac{3}{5}$

Answer: $\frac{5+4+3}{5} = \frac{12}{5}$

Explain: the lcm of $\frac{1}{2}, \frac{4}{5}$ and $\frac{3}{5}$ is 5. you will now add them

(b). $\frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{6}$

Answer: $\frac{6+4+12+2}{12}, \frac{3+3+4+1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{6}$

Explain: you will add $\frac{2}{3} + \frac{3}{4} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{5}{6}$ and you will now get your answers

Arrange these fractions in order from the smallest to the largest (ascending order)

10 (a). $\frac{1}{5}, \frac{4}{5}, \frac{3}{5}$

Answer: $\frac{1-4-3}{5} = \frac{-6}{5}$

Explain:

(b). $\frac{2}{3}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{6}$

Answer: $\frac{2-1-5}{6}, \frac{3-4-2}{6}$

Explain:

Figure 6. Sample of Learners Work on the Ordering of Fractions with the Same and Different Denominators

Drawing from the analysis of students' marked scripts above, one can note that grade 7 learners lack knowledge in addition, subtraction, multiplication, and ordering of fractions. The investigator, therefore, conclude that two errors emanated from learners' work; (1) procedural errors and (2) conceptual errors. This result corroborates the findings of, (Baidoo,2019) who contended that fractions mistakes made by students include inappropriate use of techniques and improper application of mathematical principles and generalizing rules only after seeing them work in a few specific circumstances. Also, in the findings of (Makhubele, 2021), learners' main sources of errors in fractions were attributed to the core idea ignorance, prior knowledge of the students, and improper application of the rules. Pitsi and Esther (2016) in their study also pointed out that procedural and conceptual errors committed by learners emanated from learners' inability to conceptually and procedural comprehension of fractions.

Research question two: what are the possible causes of the misconceptions and errors?

To answer question two (2) learners were interviewed. The recorded data were transcribed and coded. Three themes emerged from learners' responses to the interview questions.

The three thematic areas identified as the probable causes of the learners' misconceptions and errors when learning fractions are: (1) Learners' pre-conceived ideas (perceptions) about mathematics, (2) Methods of instruction; and (3) Cognitive abilities of learners'

Theme 1: Learners' Pre-Conceived Ideas (perceptions) about Mathematics

During the focus group, interviews, and reflection activity participants' learners note the following as a response to the cause of the errors they made in their solutions:

L1 said *'they say mathematics is hard in Senior High School, I don't want to go and do fractions there'*.

L2 also said *'because my sister and mother said mathematics is difficult that is why I don't like mathematics, especially fractions'*.

Drawing from the above extract, it can be said that learners consider fractions as one of the difficult topic in the school curriculum. This finding gives credence to the result of Yenilmez and Kocaoglu, (2010) who found that fifth-graders have difficulty understanding fractional problems. Again (Kane, Sandretto, & Heath, 2002) note that preexisting perceptions are resistant to change and difficult to break and could lead to misunderstanding basic concepts in mathematics

Theme 2: Methods of Instruction

Participating learners in the focused group interview also acknowledged that mathematics in general, and fractions, in particular, are difficult to grasp, because of how teachers handle the subject. This is exemplified by the extract below:

L3 had this to say: *"This is because our teacher always adds or subtract the top numbers together and down number together sometimes and sometimes, he finds common multiples before. I just get confused sometimes. Fractions are just hard for me"*.

L4 said *"I get confused because the formulas are many, our master said, we must remember all the formulas, additions, multiplications, and subtractions, and also LCM. Fractions are difficult"*.

Drawing from the above extract, it could be claimed that learners lack comprehension of fractional notions as they refer to mathematical operations as formulas. Also, learners do not know when to add or subtract fractions and when to even find LCM to simplify fractions, all these misunderstandings could probably be a result of how the teacher handles the topic and the teaching methods used. This finding is coherent with the findings of Kennedy, (2019) who concluded in his study that the cause of pupils' inability to solve fraction problems is attributable to teachers' lack of teaching methods and strategies to enable the pupil to study with zeal.

Theme 3: Cognitive Abilities of Learners'

From the interview transcript, L5 said '*fractions are hard and difficult to understand*'.

L6 also stated '*fractions are difficult to learn and understand and even when the teacher teaches, I just don't understand*'

L7 had this to say, '*I just don't understand fractions at all*'

Cognitive ability, which includes functions like attention, memory, and reasoning ability, is the capacity of the human brain to process, store, and retrieve information (Yueqi & Shaowei, 2021). Drawing from the extract above, most learners could have weak cognitive abilities that could have accounted for their inability to understand the concept of fractions even after being taught by their teachers as stated by one of the respondents. This finding gives credence to the finding by (Xu & Li, 2015) who conducted a study involving 4,743 junior high school students and found that short-term memory and reasoning ability students are significant predictors of mathematics learning ability and performance. Cognitive bias is the most recent challenge in understanding fractions (Liu, 2017; Krowka & Fuchs, 2019; Hacker, Kihara, & Levin, 2019). To the authors, the inability of some learners to understand ideas and procedures of fractions shows that students have diverse cognitive abilities. Due to this, the students were not able to distinguish among the whole number and ratio presentations when solving problems (Hoch et al., 2018).

Conclusion

The study's purpose was to identify misconceptions and errors amongst basic 7 learners and the causes of these errors. The study revealed the following misconceptions; overgeneralizing the idea of dealing with numerators separately from denominators as it is done in multiplication of fractions into addition and subtraction of fractions, and assuming that fractions with largest denominators are always the lesser fractions. It was also found that students committed conceptual and procedural errors in fractions. It was determined that ineffective teaching practices, learners preconceived ideas about mathematics resulted in students' lack of conceptual and procedural comprehension, which causes misconceptions and errors.

References

Abdul Ghani, S. N., & Maat, S. M. (2018). Misconception of fraction among middle-grade year four pupils at primary school. *Research on Education and Psychology*, 2(1), 111–125.

- Agbozo, K. K., & Fletcher, J. A. (2020). Pre-service teachers' understanding of selected concepts of fractions. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 7(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3722670>
- Aksoy, N. C., & Yazlik, D. O. (2017). Student errors in fractions and possible causes of these errors. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 5(11), 219–233.
- Alghazo, Y. M., & Alghazo, R. (2017). Exploring common misconceptions and errors about fractions among college students in Saudi Arabia. *International Education Studies*, 10(4), 133–140.
- Alkhateeb, M. A. (2019). Common errors in fractions and the thinking strategies that accompany them. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12(2), 399–416. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2019.12226a>
- Alon, S. (2012). Building a more complete understanding of fractions: Evidence and analysis of a classroom case study. *National Teacher Education Journal*, 5(2), 115–127.
- Deringöl, Y. (2019). Misconceptions of primary school students about the subject of fractions. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 8(1), 29–38.
- Ghani, S. N. A., & Maat, S. M. (2018). Misconception of fraction among middle grade year four pupils at primary school. *Research on Education and Psychology*, 2(1), 111–125.
- Kennedy, M. M. (2019). How we learn about teacher learning. *Review of Research in Education*, 43(1), 138–162. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0091732X19838970>
- Lee, H. J., & Boyadzhiev, I. (2020). Underprepared college students' understanding of and misconceptions with fractions. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/8487>
- Mohamed, R., Ghazali, M., & Samsudin, M. A. (2021). A systematic review on teaching fraction for understanding through representation on Web of Science database using PRISMA. *LUMAT: International Journal on Math, Science and Technology Education*, 9(1), 100–125. <https://doi.org/10.31129/lumat.9.1.1406>
- Ojose, B. (2015). *Common misconceptions in mathematics: Strategies to correct them*. University Press of America.
- Pitsi, M. E. (2016). Identifying common misconceptions and associated errors the grade 9 learners make when adding and subtracting common fractions. (Master's thesis). University of Johannesburg, South Africa.
- Redmond, A. (2009). Prospective elementary teachers' division of fractions understanding: A mixed methods study. (Doctoral dissertation). Oklahoma State University.
- Rosli, R., Goldsby, D., Onwuegbuzie, A. J., Capraro, M. M., Capraro, R. M., & Gonzalez, E. G. Y. (2020). Elementary preservice teachers' knowledge, perceptions and attitudes towards fractions: A mixed-analysis. *Journal on Mathematics Education*, 11(1), 59–76.
- Shi, Y., & Qu, S. (2021). Cognitive ability and self-control's influence on high school students' comprehensive academic performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 783673. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.783673>
- Teddle, C., & Tashakkori, A. (2012). Common “core” characteristics of mixed methods research: A review of critical issues and call for greater convergence. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 56(6), 774–788. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764211433795>

